
Agro-Tourism - Socio-Economic Aspects of Tourism

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Introduction:

The tourism is a business of providing various type of services such as transport, food, entertainment for people who are on holiday.

Keyword: Agro-Tourism, Economic Impact, Mass Tourism, Environment.

Define of Tourisms:

“It is a travel for pleasure also the theory and practice of the business of attracting according accommodation and entertainment tourist and the business of operating tours.”- Oxford English dictionary

“The Tourism more generally in terms which go beyond the common perception of tourism as being limited to holiday activity only, as people travelling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive for leisure business and other purposes.”- The World Tourism Organization

Tourism can be local and international. In the recent times, the tourism has affected economy of many countries the economic transactions have increased in many countries. World travel and tourism Council produces reports and forecast of the economic and employment impact of Travel and Tourism for 180 countries and 30 Geographic or economic regions in the world. Our 12 year forecast also provides a unique understanding of travel and tourism for the growth economic importance and social influence. These reports are a vital

tool in helping us to equip public and provide sector bodies with hard evidence of the huge value Travel and Tourism brings to the economy. So that the policy making and investment decisions support our sector

The Tourism is economically important and it growing rapidly in India. The World Travel and Tourism Council calculated that tourism generated 8.31 lakh core of the nation's GDP in 2015 and supported 3700 million jobs, of its total employment. In the recent times there have been incensing different forms of tourism. One of the alternative tourism. This form of tourism is made specific purpose. Alternative tourism combines tourist products or industrial tourist services different from the mass tourism by means of supply, organization and the human resource involve.

The mass tourism is characterized by large number of people seeking relevant to their culture holidays in popular resort destinations. Alternatives tourism is sometimes referred to as special interest tourism or responsible tourism and usually taken to me alternative forms of tourism. Alternative tourism is a form of tourism that

are consist with natural social and community values and which allow both host and guests to enjoy positive and worthwhile interaction and shared experience. Here the three influent drivers of the movement to find alternative forms of tourism.

1. The recognition of the negative impacts of convocational tourism on the environmental and social culture of the destinations.
2. The appearance of development in the lodges which mostly seed the disadvantage of growth oriented development modernization, organization, and capitalism.
3. The human nation considerations and the recognition of the rights of local populations to manage change in their communities.

Objective:

The main objective of this paper is to discuss the socio – economic and positive and negative impact of tourism.

Methodology:

This paper is mainly based on secondary data which was collected through internet, reference books and newspapers.

The alternative tourism can be seen both as a vision of the future and as an adaptation to mass tourism using this criteria. The alternative tourism exist purely a concern for the physical environment that is Agro Tourism to including Physical, economic, social and cultural consideration. Thus alternative tourism can be viewed as being synonymous with the concept of sustainable tourism development. The alternative tourism aim to shift away from mainstream heritage and traditions tourism has many potential benefits from rural areas. Town or Rural tourism is essentially and actively which takes place in the countryside it is multifaceted and may in till form agriculture, culture, nature, adventure and eco-tourism. Convent conventional tourism,

rural tourism has certain typical characteristics like it is an experience oriented the locations are sparsely populated it is predominantly in the natural environment it means with seasonally and local events and is has on prevention of culture, heritage and traditions rural tourism has may potential benefits for rural areas.

Agro Tourism:

In this world the last 35 years old the century Agro tourism appeared in international literature. There exist a parallel the world Agro tourism the two terms have the sum meaning both terms consist of two parts agri or Agro and tourism the prefix agri drives from the Latin term agri with means field. The agro comes from the Greek term agros which means soil. While tourism is a form of active recreation from one's place of residence that is inspired by cognitive recreational and sports need the combinations of fix agree with non tourism results in the formation of New world Agro tourism. Agri Tourism that means human to reach actively whose to familiarize oneself with farming activity and recreation in an agriculture environment Agro Tourism can be defined as a range of activities services and amenities provided by farmers and rural people to attract tourist to their area in order to generate tick extra income for their business.

The agro tourism a specific form of rural tourism with close relation to nature and Country side of rural areas and direct relationship to agricultural activities. The base of this tourism is mainly agricultural. The difference between the Agro Tourism and Rural Tourism is critical. In the areas where farm production is divided and highly specialized and where it is possible to observe the closed relations in the rural community. It is advisable to use the term Rural Tourism to Agro Tourism. Agro tourism is a way of responsible and Sustainable Tourism Development. This

innovative activity helps to boost up the social economic condition of the rural area by providing employment and creation the markets for the rural products.

The Socio-Economic Impact of Agro Tourism on Rural Area:

Today the agro-tourism is very important for the communities in Urban as well as Rural. Agro Tourism can have several positive impacts on rural community.

Positive Economic Impact:

- Creation of employment and reduction of unemployment rates.
- Promotion of the social-economic development of under privileged areas, diversification of economic activity, in rural areas creating conditions and opportunities for the development of other types of activity in rural areas.
- Obtaining additional sources of income for farmers (increased revenue for farmer and thus income may be adopted to investment outlets for example construction or renovation works)which results in reduced dependence on farming diversification of local economy, which in this way becomes less fluctuations.
- Obtaining additional income for business comments, and local governments of a given town associations of communes or the region.
- Overcoming income recession additionally tourism is a revival factor in rural areas and the revitalization of the rural community by offering positive of social and economic advancement.
- Extension of accommodation facilities, maintenance of existing production, cells of creation form produce contribute to the formation and development of additional

markets for food staffs and different type of local services such as crafts, Handicrafts products, and artist metalwork.

All Positive Social Impact:

- Educational functions of Agro Tourism are connected with the learning about the real world (nature culture heritage), which modifies specific attitude in relation to difference aspects of reality, (the host and guest a group of tourist family) Agro tourism is also a medium to express once feeling (learning about and respect for farmers and farm produce), Agro Tourism offices and opportunity for tourists to be creative (participation in farm work, learning a folk, craft, etc.) contribute to good health, climate conditions, food, exercise.
- Meeting new people, a possibility to make new contents and social ties, exchange of experience, or attitudes on the part of farmers and their guests, increased the tolerance in relation to different attitude, behavior or opinions, broadening of knowledge on the world and other people on the part of farm owners, encouragement to develop hobbies and interests.
- A possibility to review rural traditions, promoting respect and revival of folk traditions and culture, the development of culture in rural areas, fuller utilization and reviewed revival of creation objects in villages(community centre, sports facilities etc.)
- Gaining new skills, experience and professions learning foreign language, gaining entrepreneurial skills, actualization of the rural community, formation of new capacities in tourists their services, broadening once knowledge or

learning more about once local area, its history and attractions encouragement of social initiatives or new opportunities of for rural women.

Positive environment impacts:

- Enhanced care for the environment nature protection, creating a friendlier environment for guests and visitors.
- The development of local infrastructure water supply, sewerage systems, sewage treatment plants, roads, public transport, recreation facility which makes life in the country easier and improves the standards of living for rural populations.
- Since Agri-Tourism in the process of development uses elements of the natural environment transforming them, spatial and environmental functions include the consequences of the development of Agri Tourism for the natural and anthropogenic environments.
- Countering mass migration from rural areas (mainly of young and educated people) and the population of rural areas.
- Improved aesthetic value of houses and areas in their vacancy, care for the aesthetic value of village, houses, streets and other public space aesthetic enhancement of villages.

Conclusion:

If a proper strategic planning is done for Agro tourism it could bring lot of benefit to our society. It could be a sustainable revenue generating project for rural development. It can help in flow to resources are urban to the rural economy. It can prevent migration of rural people to urban. Both short term and long term planning implementing and monitoring are vital in avoiding damage to rural areas environmental management local involvement, sound legislation, sustainable marketing and realistic planning are crucial for development of agro tourism. Agro tourism is emerging as an important instrument for sustainable Human Development including poverty, employment generate, generation environment, regression and development of remote areas and advancement of women and other disadvantage groups in the country apart from promoting social integration and international understanding. The government should promote Agro Tourism to ensure sustainable economic development and positive social change.

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